

INFLUENCE OF HISTORICAL PLACES FOR DEVELOPING OF TOURISM INDUSTRY IN SAMARKAND CITY

Shodikulova Mokhigul Ulugbekovna

MA student of Silk Road International University
of Tourism and Cultural
Heritage

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Annotation: This article provides information at increasing the role of historical places for developing of tourism industry in Samarkand city via presenting the rich history of city, to show culture, to introduce unique traditions, to visit and enjoy from travelling to sightseeing buildings of region to the world tourism community, to show tourism potential of Samarkand and make it favourite touristic destinations for visitors, tourists, revive cultural tourism and flow tourists travelling around city.

Key words: Historical places, cultural heritage tourism, tourism ability of Samarkand city, tourist destination, tourist flow, tourist motivation.

Samarkand is the second largest city in Uzbekistan and it has more two thousand year history. The city was a “key point” and central crossroads of the “Great Silk Road” and civilization which situated between China and Europe, served as one of the most important centers of trade, science and culture in the medieval East. Samarkand with its rich cultural history and values, has long made a worthy contribution to the civilization of the peoples of the world and has serves as a unique bridge between ancient time and present life of humanity.

To show recognition of Uzbekistan as competitive tourism country, UNWTO opened its regional office in Samarkand in 2004. This office coordinates the development of tourism on the Silk Road. There are only two offices in the world - in Japan and Uzbekistan.

Due to its rich history and historical places, great ancestors, city became one of the tourist visiting city in present time. Ancient and architectural buildings of the city, picturesque and beautiful nature creates great opportunities for the tourism industry. Cultural heritage is essential, because of, it influences strongly to our sense of identity, loyalties and behavior.

To build very beautiful city or historical places took long time, and skillful masters of their work, and knowledgeable experienced builders completed it during building historical places of Samarkand.

The tourist destination is a main element of the tourism industry. It could be expressed as an area with all kinds of comfortability, accomodations and

services to meet the different needs of visitors. The tourist destinations and their brand attraction tourists, motivate the visit. The brand images and heritage buildings of Samarkand city, serves to gain high reputation between world leader countries which tourism developed. It includes country's image, to show tourism potential of Samarkand city through cultural tourism, increase of influential factors of developing tourism industry, entry and exit visas and safety tourism.

City blessed by its perfect geographical location, climate condition, hospitality and tourism potential. Samarkand entered to the list of UNESCO's World Heritage List in 2001 with its ancient historical monuments, it is important for tourists who come to city, get interesting information about history in front of it. And it is one of the reason being famous place for visitors and to increase reputation of heritage tourism.

This benefit gives privilege creation of new work places, different services related to tourism, preparing qualified personnel in tourism field and impact to economy of country with financial incomes.

Travelling especially to historical places, familiarize Samarkand with the world community, future development of tourism prospects through developing cultural tourism and pay attention to all architectural monuments, buildings, shows the high potential of tourism in Samarkand city.

There are more than 140 historical monuments such as mausoleums, museums, temples, mosques and etc. It is planned to make Samarkand a tourist hub of Uzbekistan.

The buildings that were built in the middle century in territory of Samarkand city and their beauty with unique view can rank a high evaluation and one of the reason to visit in Samarkand.

Because, tourists not visit only for sightseeings, also they want to know our history, to visit to museums, to participate different musical festivals or holidays, to acquaintance with uzbek traditions, to enjoy our theatres scenes and several day to live with helpful and hospitable people.

Due to popularity of our historical monuments and ancient great Samarkand visitors can not imagine them separately in their mind. If you speak about Samarkand they think about magic city with historical buildings at the same time. It shows how the city takes important role in history and tourism industry of the world.

Every place has it is deep interesting history and formation during different years. They are "visit card" of Samarkand and show the high developed

cultural heritage tourism of city in the world tourism. Researches show that, 63% of the tourists visit directly to architectures for a purpose of traveling. Architectural resources of Samarkand worth to praise. The main historical places of city located in the center and old part of city. All of them have the same stylistic appearance. The design is expressed with huge arched portals and high blue domes, exquisite ornamentation from tiled majolica. The walls have geometric ornaments connecting the stars, a swastika with the names of Allah, the Prophet and Islamic good wishes. The culture of that time can be felt through these ornaments. It is difficult to name all the places on the list, since the city itself is an open-air museum. The majority of the most popular historical places are located very close to each other. The most tourist visiting and heart of city is Registan square (15th century), the next and other beautiful buildings which connected with Amir Temur's period are Gur-Emir Mausoleum (13th -15th century), Shakhi-Zinda (11th century), Bibi -Khanym Mosque (14th -15th centuries), Bibi-Khanym Mausoleum (1399-1404), Khazret-Khyzr Mosque (1823), Khoja Doniyor Mausoleum (15th century), Rukhabad Mausoleum (1380 y.), Abu Mansur Maturidi Mausoleum (944), Ishratkhan (15th century), Khoja Daniyar Tomb, Tillya-Kori Madrasah (17th century), Ensemble Abdi Birun (17th century), Sherdor Madrasah (17th century). A popular place for tourists to visit is the Ancient Settlement of Afrasiab, where people can get to know the history and formation of the city, and the Monument to Amir Temur.

According to statistics of 2022 year, it shows in 2022 the Registan ensemble in Samarkand region was visited by 1,27,951 local and foreign tourists. Export of tourism services amounted to 97.7 million dollars. 100,000 more foreign tourists will have been attracted, and the volume of exports in the sector will have been expected to reach 110.0 million dollars by the end of the year. Currently, the average stay of foreign tourists at the destination is 2.6 days (1 day's cost is 65-213 US dollars). More than 22,400 jobs have been created in tourism and related services in 2022 year.

In 2014, Samarkand appeared in the list of, "The 50 cities you must see during your lifetime". Keeping originality and preserving historical monuments of Samarkand is one of the main way of saving our heritage. And it is under control of our government and tourism department. In 2019, Samarkand was chosen as the place for the meeting of Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) in 2022.

In general it will have high economic impact of the developing tourism to economy by showing heritage tourism building providing high services to

visitors. Concentrating famous historical buildings of city, and taking into consideration current situation that have in tourism Samarkand shows great opportunities in this sphere.

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